

Propagation Dependent Base Station Positioning in UAV-assisted Cell-less Networks

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Abstract—Enhancing the reliability and throughput of modern terrestrial cellular and ultra-dense networks (UDNs) through unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) has become an important topic in wireless communications research. A key element in the implementation of UAV-assisted networks is the aerial base station’s positioning. This work employs the advancements in channel modeling for air-to-ground links to evaluate the system’s throughput in different propagation scenarios. The UAV is associated to the low-throughput users, which are ordinarily served by the ground-based access point (AP) within a UDN. The UAV position that provides the best performance is selected for all path-loss (PL) models, and the experiment is performed for different coefficients (periods) of update for the UE associations between the UAV and the AP. System throughput of up to 120 Mbps is achieved.

Index Terms—Cell-less, path-loss, propagation, UAV-assisted networks, user association, UAV placement, resource allocation

I. INTRODUCTION

The increasing density and diversification of both current and emerging wireless communication standards are motivated by the host of modern applications that play an increasing role in our daily lives, but also place progressively higher demands in terms of usable bandwidth, low latency and fast processing of radio frequency (RF) signals [1]. Essential for these requirements’ satisfaction is the flexible allocation of network resources and spectrum utilization efficiency among the users in applications such as vehicular communications, enhanced mobile broadband connections, user-centric ultra-dense networks (UDNs), Industry 4.0 and Internet of Things (IoT). These technologies are facilitated and enhanced by employing UAVs as aerial base stations (ABSs) that support and boost the service reliability of ground base stations (GBSs) by associating the users with low throughput, to the ABSs [2]–[4]. Therefore, the implementation of UAV-assisted cell-less networks relies on the three-dimensional (3D) ABS positioning, which is an important topic in the relevant literature. It

is based on either predefined conditions, the user equipment (UE) movement, or the traffic load of the GBSs. The authors of [3] consider 3D UAV placement driven by identifying the locations with underutilized spectrum in a terrestrial network, and to maximize the number of users associated with the ABS, thus increasing their throughput. The links between the GBSs and the UEs is not included in the system model. Up to 125 UEs are served by the ABS, reaching system throughput close to 300 Mbps. A related scenario is simulated in [5] to evaluate a reinforcement learning approach to ABS placement and channel distribution for the UAV-UE links, achieving average throughput of up to 1.3 Mbps per user. Further, in [4] the ABS placement is driven by the target of throughput fairness constrained by the UAVs’ energy consumption via stochastic gradient descent. In this scenario, the UAVs provide backhaul for the GBSs. A similar system model is explored for emergency communications via UAVs that operate within specific regions of space, and provide both coverage for UEs and backhaul for GBSs in [6]. The UAVs’ trajectories are estimated through RL based on the UEs’ movements. Throughput of up to 88 Mbps is obtained. The authors of [7] design the UAV’s placement as a Markov decision process, and through the use of radio environment maps (REMs), provide wireless charging to the UEs. The links between both the ABS and the UEs, the GBSs and the UEs, are considered. Throughput of close to 250 Mbps is reached. REMs are also employed in [8] to facilitate the ABS’ placement and its association to the UEs through particle swarm optimization. The proposed method aims to it increase the minimum network throughput, and achieves improvement of nearly 11 bps/Hz. UAV-assisted vehicle-to-everything network operating in non-orthogonal multiple access is considered in [9]. Terrestrial users are associated to the UAVs on the basis of their signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), obtaining throughputs of up to 4 bps/Hz.

This work focuses on the 3D ubiquitous connectivity and mobility expressed in the capacity gains provided by the integration of an ABS, which because of its rapid aerial flight, provides better coverage to low-throughput UEs [2]. Due to the dynamic characteristics of air-to-ground (A2G) channels depending on the UAV’s operational height and the physical environment, a number of path-loss (PL) models have been established in the literature [10], and therefore, they are applied for the ABS-UE links to evaluate the network’s throughput for six default baseline UAV positions within the

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Fig. 1. UAV-assisted cell-less scenario.

ABS operational area. The considered PL models are namely log-distance Alpha-Beta, PL dual slope, two ray PL, and modified two ray PL. After the best position is chosen, the throughput is compared for different values of the update coefficient C_U , i.e. the duration between two updates of the ABS positioning and UE associations. The ABS is associated to the low-throughput UEs, which are ordinarily served by the AP within a UDN scenario with only a single section of the UDN being considered (UDN operational area). To facilitate this process it is assumed that the UAV exchanges overhead control messages with the AP. The results illustrate the best position over which the ABS is assumed to hover during the simulation's runtime. The propagation scenarios' influence on the network's throughput is also characterized. The contribution of this article is summarized as follows:

- A method of operation for the UAV-assisted UDN consisting of ABS placement and UE associations. It determines the best positioning of the ABS from a set of predetermined positions. The UE associations to the ABS are determined by the throughput that the UEs obtain from the AP. The system's performance is evaluated for four prominent propagation scenarios and varied update coefficients. Consequently, throughput of up to 120 Mbps is achieved and the best ABS position is identified.

The rest of this paper is organized in this manner. Section II describes the system model and the proposed solution. The results are discussed in Section III. Finally, the conclusions are given in Section IV.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

This section provides a brief description of the system model and the channel models for the AP-UE, AP-UAV, and UAV-UE links. The system model is presented in Fig. 1, consisting of a stationary AP and N_{UE} UEs, which are associated with it by default. The set \mathbb{U} denotes all UEs, with $|\mathbb{U}| = N_{UE}$. The UAV covers only the ABS operational area, denoted as \mathbb{A} , it obtains the UEs throughput from the AP, and decides which UEs to associate with. The UEs move in 3D within the UDN operational area. The PL between the UAV and UEs, and the AP and the UEs, are determined using

separate statistical models [10], [11]. The ABS and the AP operate on two separate sets out of all N_{ch} available bands - $\mathcal{F} = \{f_0, f_1, \dots, f_{N_{\mathcal{F}}-1}\}$ and $\mathcal{G} = \{g_0, g_1, \dots, g_{N_{\mathcal{G}}-1}\}$, respectively, where $N_{\mathcal{G}} = \delta_{\mathcal{G}} * N_{ch}$ and $\delta_{\mathcal{G}}$ is the portion of channels that are to be allocated to the AP users, $N_{\mathcal{F}} + N_{\mathcal{G}} = N_{ch}$. The UAV operates within the volume of space \mathbb{A} where it serves its associated UEs for $N_s = C_U$ serving iterations. These UEs form the set \mathbb{U}_a , with $N_{\mathbb{U}_a} = |\mathbb{U}_a|$, while the rest of the users form the set \mathbb{U}_u , with $N_{\mathbb{U}_u} = |\mathbb{U}_u|$, and $N_{\mathbb{U}_a} + N_{\mathbb{U}_u} = N_{UE}$. The 3D UAV operational space is divided into $M_{\mathbb{A}} = M^3$ equidistant locations that signify the UAV positioning and define \mathbb{A} with M being the axis resolution.

The stationary AP is associated to all N_{UE} UEs by default with their movements being modeled via the random walk algorithm. First, the UEs are placed in the simulation area according to the Matern distribution with density λ_{UE} , which determines N_{UE} , and a minimum distance between two UEs of $d_{min,UE}$. At each consecutive iteration, the UEs' locations change with a random speed $\theta \in [0; \theta_{max}]$, where θ_{max} is the UE's maximal speed, and direction according to a randomly selected angle $\phi \in [0; 2\pi]$. The UEs' movements are unrestrained within the UDN operational area. The SNR $\sigma_{UE_i}^{\mathcal{W}_i}$ at the i -th UE with the AP operating on the set \mathcal{W}_i of channels allocated to this UE where $|\mathcal{W}_i| \geq 1$, is represented as:

$$\sigma_{UE_i}^{\mathcal{W}_i} = \frac{P_{R,UE}^{\mathcal{W}_i}}{P_0 * N_{F_{UE}}}, P_{R,UE}^{\mathcal{W}_i} = h_t P_{t,T}^{\mathcal{W}_i} + P_0, \quad (1)$$

where $P_{t,T}^{\mathcal{W}_i}$ is the transmission power of the serving node $t = \{AP; ABS\}$ that the UE is associated to (AP or ABS). Then, the $P_{R,UE}^{\mathcal{W}_i}$ is the received power of the UE, h_t is the channel coefficient that describes the PL. The overall network throughput \mathcal{T} is comprised of the sum of each user's individual capacity \mathcal{T}_{UE_i} :

$$\mathcal{T} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{UE}} \mathcal{T}_{UE_i} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{UE}} |\mathcal{W}_i| \mathcal{B} \log_2(1 + \sigma_{UE_i}^{\mathcal{W}_i}), \quad (2)$$

where $|\mathcal{W}_i|$ denote the number of channels allocated to each UE accordingly, with \mathcal{B} being the width per channel.

To model the wireless channels the UAV and the AP and UEs, four prominent PL models [10] are used with the system's throughput being compared for each of them. These are the log-distance Alpha-Beta (denoted as AB), PL dual slope (DS), two ray PL ($2R$), and modified two ray PL ($2RM$), which consider the ABS operating at low altitudes, i.e. its height H_a being below 30 m, and utilize the following parameters: the 3D distance $d = \sqrt{d_x^2 + d_y^2 + d_z^2}$ with d_x , d_y and d_z being the distances between the transmitter and the receiver in the x , y and z axes, $\alpha = 2.9$, $\gamma_1 = 0.74$ and $\gamma_2 = 2.29$ are the PL exponents, $\beta = 7.4$ is the intercept point with the line $d = 1$ m, $\sigma_{PL} = 6.2$ is the PL standard deviation, H_T and H_R are the heights of the transmitter and the receiver, respectively, $d_b = 9$ is the break distance, $G_l(H_a) = 15$ is the direct path coefficient, $G_r(H_a) = 5$ describe the reflected path, while $\gamma(H_a) = 3.5$ - the height-dependent propagation.

The AP-UEs links are modeled through a 3GPP popular probabilistic n -th piece model [11] which accounts for both line-of-sight (LOS) and non-line-of-sight (NLOS) components of the received signal. It includes the coefficients $A_\delta = 10^{-10.38}$, $A_{NL} = 10^{-14.54}$, $\alpha_\delta = 2.09$ and $\alpha_{NL} = 3.75$ that describe the channel LOS and NLOS characteristics according to the standard [11], the parameters $R_1 = 156$ m, $R_2 = 30$ m and $d_1 = \frac{R_1}{\ln(10)}$, with $\delta = 8.5$ m being the absolute antenna height difference between the transmitter and receiver.

This system model is implemented through the method of operations described in Algorithm 1. First we define, the sets of channels \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{F} , system parameters $N_{UE}, N_I, N_{ch}, C_U, P_{ABS,T}, P_{AP,T}, \delta_G$, the simulation environment lengths for each of the axes S_x, S_y , and S_z . The algorithm operation follows the following processes. First, the AP serves all UEs for $N_s = C_U$ iterations, and the AP provides feedback to the ABS regarding the UEs throughput $\mathcal{T}_{UE_i} |_{i=1}^{N_{UE}}$. The ABS is positioned at a particular position $L \in \mathbb{A}$ preliminary set with the coordinates $[S_{x,L}, S_{y,L}, S_{z,L}]$, with $s_{x,L} \in [-\frac{S_x}{2}, \frac{S_x}{2}]$, $s_{y,L} \in [-\frac{S_y}{2}, \frac{S_y}{2}]$, $s_{z,L} \in [-\frac{S_z}{2}, \frac{S_z}{2}]$. The ABS associates with the UEs that form the set \mathbb{U}_a according to the following criterion \mathcal{C} : $\mathbb{U}_a = \{u_i\}, \{i \mid \mathcal{T}_i \geq \mathcal{T}_0\}, i \in \{1, \dots, N_{UE} - 2\}$, $\mathbb{U}_u = \mathbb{U} \setminus \mathbb{U}_a$, i.e. those, the throughput of which, is below than the threshold \mathcal{T}_0 , while the rest of the UEs (the set \mathbb{U}_u) will continue to be served by the AP for the following N_s iterations. The sets of channels \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} are allocated among the users associated to the UAV and the AP, respectively, for the duration of the following N_s iterations. Finally, the network throughput \mathcal{T} is calculated and the UEs movements are modified. The overall system bandwidth is $BW = N_{ch} * \mathcal{B}$.

Algorithm 1 Method of operations for ABS positioning and UE associations

Input: $\mathcal{G}, \mathcal{F}, N_{UE}, N_I, N_{ch}, N_m, P_{AP,T}, P_{ABS,T}, \delta_G, S_x, S_y, S_z, C_U, \lambda_{UE}, l$

Output: \mathcal{T}

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1: for  $i = 1$  to  $N_I$  iterations do
2:   if  $i == 0$  then
3:     Allocate all  $N_{ch}$  channels to the AP for all UEs
4:   end if
5:   if mod( $i, N_s$ ) == 0 then
6:     Set the ABS at location  $L$ 
7:     Allocate the sets of channels  $\mathcal{F}$  and  $\mathcal{G}$ 
8:     Determine  $\mathbb{U}_a$  and  $\mathbb{U}_u$  using  $\mathcal{C}$ 
9:   end if
10:  Calculate  $\mathcal{T} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{UE}} \mathcal{T}_{UE_i}$ 
11:  The UEs move with speed of  $\theta$  at an angle of  $\phi$ 
12: end for

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III. SIMULATION RESULTS

This Section outlines the parameters (Table I) under which the simulations are performed, and also details the findings and their significance. The simulation is run on an AMD Ryzen Threadripper 2990WX 32-Core Processor at 3.00 GHz,

64 GB of random access memory (RAM), solid state drive (SSD), and an NVIDIA GeForce 2080 RTX Ti (12 GB) graphical processing unit (GPU), Python 3.9 and TensorFlow 2.10. The simulation space boundaries are denoted as $[-(S_x/2); (S_x/2)]$ for the x -axis, $[-(S_y/2); (S_y/2)]$ for the y -axis, and $[-(S_z/2); (S_z/2)]$ for the z -axis. The AP is positioned at coordinates $[14.95, 62.93, 1.5]$ and the UEs are distributed through the Matern method with density of λ_{UE} . The UAV operational space is limited within the axes lengths of S_x, S_y , and $S_z - 5$. Two sets of simulations are performed to evaluate the \mathcal{T} for the control variables that describe each respective experiment, with the parameters from Table I being constant. These are the UAV position L (described by its coordinates) and the update coefficient C_U . The simulation is

TABLE I
SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
λ_{UE}	10
N_I	10^5
S_x, S_y, S_z	150, 150, 15 m
\mathcal{B}	180 kHz
N_{ch}	55
F_c	2 GHz
$P_{AP,T}, P_{ABS,T}$	24 dBm
N_{FUE}	9 dB
$d_{min,UE}$	0.3 m
δ_{max}	3 km/h
δ_V	0.5

first performed for six different positions at which UAV hovers as it serves the UEs, for each of the four PL scenarios. The cumulative distribution functions (CDFs) of their throughputs are illustrated in Fig. 2. These positions are defined through their coordinates as follows. The position L_R denotes a random set of coordinates within \mathbb{A} . For the other positions being predetermined, their coordinates are presented in Table II. They represent the center L_C of the simulation space, and four positions ($L_{E1}, L_{E2}, L_{E3}, L_{E4}$) that correspond to the four corners of the simulation space but with some internal margin of 10 m. The selection of these coordinates represent the general default positions.

TABLE II
COORDINATES OF UAV POSITIONS

Positioning Case	$s_{x,L}$	$s_{y,L}$	$s_{z,L}$
L_C	5	5	12.67
L_{E1}	-65	-65	12.67
L_{E2}	65	-65	12.67
L_{E3}	65	65	12.67
L_{E4}	-65	65	12.67

Notably, the highest and lowest throughputs (of up to 120 and 90 Mbps) are achieved for the AB and DS PL models, respectively. The throughputs for each UAV position have the same variation between each other in all models. These tendencies show the characteristics of the propagation models. The DS model is characterized by dynamic fading with very

Fig. 2. CDFs of \mathcal{T} for different positions in each of the PL models.

high variation due to the approximation of the effects of obstacles in UAV operational heights of under 30 m [12]. On the other hand, the *AB* model has the simplest description of the signal propagation as it uses only a single slope for the PL exponent, thus achieving the lowest losses. As for the *2R* and *2RM* models, the PL is more significant for the latter because it considers the effect of ground reflections with the varying UAV height, to a much greater degree. The results for L_{E3} and L_C are similar with about 10% higher throughput for the former position as it covers the most UEs during the simulation time. Thus, it is established as the best position for this scenario. These results are supported by the distributions of the received signal strength (RSS) $P_{R,UE}^{W_i}, W_i \in \mathbb{U}_a$ of the UEs, which are associated with the ABS on the corresponding channels, which are of the set \mathbb{U}_a , as illustrated in Fig. 3. For more clarity, the CDFs of the RSS at only the positions with the lowest (L_{E1}) and highest (L_C and L_{E3}) throughputs, are illustrated. It is observed that significantly higher (up to 15 dBm) RSS levels are obtained for the L_{E3} position for all PL models in comparison to the RSS for both the L_{E1} and L_C positions. The bigger PL in the *2RM*, *2R* and *DS* models is reflected by the CDF's convergence which is reached for -105, -85, and -100 dBm, respectively. In spite of the CDF for the *AB* model converging at the same RSS as the *2R*, i.e. -85 dBm, its distribution includes between 5 and 10% more samples for their respective RSS levels in $P_{R,UE}^{W_i} > -120$ dBm. For the *2RM* and *AB* cases, the amount

of measurements that have RSS over -120 dBm, is significantly smaller by 25 and 50%, respectively.

Another simulation is performed for the best position (L_{E3}) of the UAV but considering different values of the $C_U = \{100, 300, 500, 1000\}$, for each of the four PL scenarios. The CDFs of their throughputs are illustrated in Fig. 4. The characteristics of the propagation models have, once again, a significant influence on the results as the more complex cases (*2R* and *2RM*) have a much more notable variation in the throughput as they consider ground reflections and shadowing. The most notable feature of the results is that the \mathcal{T} distributions vary very slightly from each other. During the simulation time, there are periods and their corresponding UE movements, for which a particular C_U leads to a greater throughput as the UE associations are updated more or less frequently. Therefore, in the evaluated scenario, a higher C_U may be chosen as it will lead to less exchange of overhead messages between the AP and the ABS regarding the UE associations.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This work presents a method of operation for an UAV-assisted UDN consisting of ABS placement and UE associations. It determines the best positioning of the ABS from a set of predetermined positions. The UE associations to the ABS are determined by the throughput that the UEs obtain from the AP. Four propagation scenarios are employed for modeling the air-to-ground links, and the throughput is evaluated for each

Fig. 3. CDFs of $P_{R,UE}^{W_i}$ for the positions of L_C , L_{E1} , and L_{E3} in each of the PL models.

Fig. 4. CDFs of \mathcal{T} for the L_{E3} position and the different C_U in each of the PL models.

of the UAV placement positions. The system's performance is evaluated for four prominent propagation scenarios and varied update coefficients. The results illustrate the best position over which the ABS is assumed to hover during the simulation's runtime. The propagation scenarios' influence on the network's throughput is also characterized through the throughput and RSS distribution. This work provides motivation for further research into ABS placement via radio environment measurements and 3D spectrum characterization, as well as adaptive UE association period.

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